

BC-SIM-TR-034 SIMBIO-SYS ICO4 Interchannel Test REPORT

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document contains the results and the discussion about the Interchannel Test performed during the Instrument Check Out Phase (ICO#4) for the Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYSTEM (SIMBIO-SYS) described in [RD.1].

1.2 Reference Documents

- [RD.1] BC-SIM-PL-006_-_SIMBIO-SYS_Checkout_04_Test_Summary_Issue1_Revision0, [10.20371/INAF/TechRep/204](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/204)
- [RD.2] BC-SIM-TN-003_-_Reports_and_Note_Layout_and_Flow, [10.20371/INAF/TechRep/179](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/179)
- [RD.3] BC-ALS-TN-00099 MPO PFM Monitoring Thermistors Location
- [RD.4] BC-SIM-TR-031_-_STC_ICO#04_report, [10.20371/INAF/TechRep/208](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/208)
- [RD.5] BC-SIM-TR-032_-_HRIC_ICO#04_report, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8366034>
- [RD.6] BC-SIM-TR-033_-_VIHI_ICO#04_report
- [RD.7] BC-SIM-TR-021_-_SIMBIO-SYS_ICO#02_Test_Report_Issue1_Revision0, [10.20371/INAF/TechRep/146](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/146)
- [RD.8] BC-SIM-TN-008_-_SIMBIO-SYS_FOP_update_after_ICO#02, [10.20371/INAF/TechRep/162](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/162)
- [RD.9] BC-SIM-GAF-TN-113 rev.0_TEC Control Parameters Revision for Commissioning_F1
- [RD.10] BC-SIM-TR-030_-_EGSE_ICO#04_report, [10.20371/INAF/TechRep/205](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/205)
- [RD.11] BC-SIM-TR-021 SIMBIO-SYS Instrument CheckOut #02 Test Report, [10.20371/INAF/TechRep/146](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/146)
- [RD.12] BC-SIM-TR-029 SIMBIO-SYS ICO#03 Test Report [10.20371/INAF/TechRep/201](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/201)

1.3 Acronyms

ACK	Acknowledgment
ADC	Analogical Digit Converter

APID	Application Process IDentifier
ASW	Application SoftWare
CM	Color Mode
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DSNU	Dark Signal Not Uniformity
FOP	Flight Operation Procedure
FPA	Focal Plane Assembly
HK	HouseKepping
HRIC	High spatial Resolution Imaging Channel
ICO	Instrument CheckOut
IT	Integration Time
ME	Main Electronics
NECP	Near Earth Commissioning Phase
OBCP	On-Board Control Procedure
OB	Optical Bench
OBSW	On Board Software
PDOR	Payload Direct Operation Request
POR	Payload Operation Request
PDS	Planetary Data System
PE	Proximity Electronics
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
PSC	Packet Sequence Control
RT	Repetition Time
SIMBIO-SYS	Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYStem
SSC	Source Sequence Count
SSMM	Solid State Mass Memory
STC	STereo imaging Channel
S/C	SpaceCraft
TC	TeleCommand
TEC	Thermo-Electric Cooler
TM	Telemetry
VIHI	VIsible and Hyper-spectral Imaging channel
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

1.4 Document Format and Repository

This document is compliant with the SIMBIO-SYS Report and Note Layout and Flow [RD.2] and will be archived on the SIMBIO-SYS ZENODO community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/?p=SIMBIO-SYS>), on the INAF Open Access repository and the SIMBIO-SYS team Archive.

1.5 Document Organization

This document is organized in sections whose topics are listed as follows:

- Section 2 – SIMBIO-SYS thermal environment description, with a brief description of the aboard units and sensors used to control the operative temperature of the instrument during the test,
- Section 3 – Interchannel test results and discussion,
- Section 4 – Conclusions on the ICO#04 activities are reported.

2 SIMBIO-SYS thermal environment description

The SIMBIO-SYS thermal environment is controlled by means of the Space-Craft (S/C) dedicated Cold Fingers (CFs) and several thermal sensors which are described in the following subsections.

2.1 SIMBIO-SYS CF sensors

In the following table the list of CF temperature sensors for the three channels is reported. To note that all sensors are fixed on the S/C CF.

Channel	Sensor name	ESA ID	THALES ID
HRIC	MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-HRIC-CF	NRUD2079	THT-B6T133
STC	MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-STC-CF	NRUD2087	THT-B6T136
VIHI	MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-VIHI-CF	NRUD2091	THT-B6T137

Table 1: CF sensors of the SIMBIO-SYS channels together with their reference to ESA and Theles Alenia nomenclature (see [RD.3] for details)

For more details on their positions see [RD.3].

2.2 SIMBIO-SYS thermal sensors

For the monitoring of its thermal behaviour, the SIMBIO-SYS instrument is equipped by the following sensors:

- **STC**

PACKET ID: YSS40002		
Param ID	Param Name	Unit
NSS21040	Temperature FPA1	K
NSS21041	Temperature FPA2	K
NSS21042	Temperature PE	K
NSS21043	Temp FPA_Package	K
NSS21044	Temp OpticalBench	K

Table 2: Main STC temperature sensors.

See [RD.4] for more details on their definition and position.

- **HRIC**

PACKET ID: YSS40001		
Param ID	Param Name	Unit
NSS11040	Temperature FPA1	K
NSS11041	Temperature FPA2	K
NSS11042	Temperature PE	K
NSS11043	Temp TIRD filter	K
NSS11044	Temp FPA package	K

Table 3: Main HRIC temperature sensors

See [RD.5] for more details on their definition and position.

- **VIHI**

PACKET ID: YSS40003		
Param ID	Param Name	Unit
NSS31040	Temperature FPA1	K
NSS31041	Temperature FPA2	K
NSS31042	Temperature PE	K
NSS31062	Temp Spectrometer	K
NSS31063	Temp Calibration unit	K

Table 4: Main VIHI temperature sensors.

See [RD.6] for more details on their definition and position.

3 SIMBIO-SYS Interchannel Test

The InterChannel test was performed during ICO04 thanks to the planning of a unique test: the SIMBIO-SYS Interference Test

3.1 SIMBIO-SYS Interference Test

3.1.1 Test Description

The aim of this test is to evaluate if and how the cameras (i.e., HRIC and STC) detector reset fluctuations change (raised during ICO2 and reported as Open Issue 1 in [RD.7]) with respect to the Repetition Time (RT) parameter contained in their Science TC.

In addition, the test will indicate if the operativity of the VIHI channel influences or not such a fluctuation.

In particular, the test lasts about 1.5 hour with:

1. **HRIC**: 4 64x128 pixels acquisitions with RT = 0.5, 1, 1.5 and 2 s
2. **STC**: the 4 HRIC acquisitions are repeated 4 times in each of which STC acquires the Win-x with changing its RT between 2 and 1 s
3. **VIHI**: it acquires continuously a full frame in nominal operation conditions to detect possible interference with the cameras

3.1.2 Commanding

Considering the goal of the Interference Test, all channels were off before its start (only ME was on – see [RD.1]) so, before executing it, it was necessary to switch-on the channels.

After that, the test has been performed through the execution of a PDORs named "PDOR_BPSS00688_ SIMBIOSYS_ALL_ICO#4_interference_test" (see attachments of [RD.1]).

A detailed timeline of the test is shown in Table 5 and Table 6.

Timing	FOP ID	FOP Name
00:00:00	ASSF320A	STC OutF SURF X v01
00:05:00	ASSF100A	HRICSciShortIntPFREE v03
00:08:00	ASSF110A	HRIC STOP Science v01
00:08:01	ASSF100A	HRICSciShortIntPFREE v03
00:14:01	ASSF110A	HRIC STOP Science v01
00:14:02	ASSF100A	HRICSciShortIntPFREE v03
00:23:02	ASSF110A	HRIC STOP Science v01
00:23:03	ASSF100A	HRICSciShortIntPFREE v03
00:28:00	ASSF368A	STC STOP Science v01
00:37:03	ASSF110A	HRIC STOP Science v01
00:37:04	ASSF320A	STC OutF SURF X v01
00:42:04	ASSF100A	HRICSciShortIntPFREE v03
00:45:04	ASSF110A	HRIC STOP Science v01
00:45:05	ASSF100A	HRICSciShortIntPFREE v03

00:51:05	ASSF110A	HRIC STOP Science v01
00:51:06	ASSF100A	HRICSciShortIntPFREE v03
01:00:06	ASSF110A	HRIC STOP Science v01
01:00:07	ASSF100A	HRICSciShortIntPFREE v03
01:05:00	ASSF368A	STC STOP Science v01
01:14:07	ASSF110A	HRIC STOP Science v01

Table 5: Timeline of the Interference Test with the references to the commanded FOPs (see [RD.7]) – first part.

After the VIHI channel power-on (together with the upload of the optimized parameters for the Thermo Electric Cooler (TEC) soft start – see [RD.9]), the same sequence has been repeated with also VIHI acquisitions:

Timing	FOP ID	FOP Name
01:30:00	ASSF512A	VIHISciMode Var IT v02 (*)
01:30:01	ASSF320A	STC OutF SURF X v01
01:35:01	ASSF100A	HRICSciShortIntPFREE v03
01:38:01	ASSF110A	HRIC STOP Science v01
01:38:02	ASSF100A	HRICSciShortIntPFREE v03
01:44:03	ASSF110A	HRIC STOP Science v01
01:44:03	ASSF100A	HRICSciShortIntPFREE v03
01:45:00	ASSF512A	VIHISciMode Var IT v02 (*)
01:53:03	ASSF110A	HRIC STOP Science v01
01:53:04	ASSF100A	HRICSciShortIntPFREE v03
01:58:01	ASSF368A	STC STOP Science v01
02:00:00	ASSF512A	VIHISciMode Var IT v02 (*)
02:07:05	ASSF320A	STC OutF SURF X v01
02:12:05	ASSF100A	HRICSciShortIntPFREE v03
02:15:00	ASSF512A	VIHISciMode Var IT v02 (*)
02:15:06	ASSF100A	HRICSciShortIntPFREE v03
02:21:06	ASSF110A	HRIC STOP Science v01
02:21:06	ASSF100A	HRICSciShortIntPFREE v03
02:25:00	ASSF514A	VIHI STOP Science v01 (*)
02:30:08	ASSF100A	HRICSciShortIntPFREE v03
02:35:01	ASSF368A	STC STOP Science v01
02:44:08	ASSF110A	HRIC STOP Science v01

Table 6: Timeline of the Interference Test with the references to the commanded FOPs (see [RD.7]) – second part. TCs rejected by the Application SoftWare (ASW) are indicated with a '*' sign.

Following figure shows the RT used during the acquisition by STC (in RED) and HRIC (in BLUE).

Figure 1: RT schema between HRIC and STC during Interference Test.

As described in [RD.6], during the execution of VIHI Performance Test, an issue occurred the determine the powering off of the channel. As a result, the Interference Test has been done just with the cameras. The resulting executions TeleCommand (TC) database derived by means of the Electric Ground Segment Equipment (EGSE) telemetry-to-raw pipeline is reported in Table 7 and Table 8 (see [RD.10] for details).

EGSE_TC#	1 st acq (UTC)	Duration (s)	# acq
1	2020-12-14T23:46:00.065134	179.5	360
2	2020-12-14T23:49:01.035576	360	360
3	2020-12-14T23:55:11.036520	529.5	354
4	2020-12-15T00:08:35.038650	566	284
5	2020-12-15T00:23:04.061151	179.5	360
6	2020-12-15T00:26:05.036522	360	360
7	2020-12-15T00:32:06.037541	538.5	360
8	2020-12-15T00:41:07.039139	838	420
9	2020-12-15T01:16:01.035508	538.5	360
10	2020-12-15T01:19:02.036132	359	360
11	2020-12-15T01:25:03.037259	538.5	360
12	2020-12-15T01:34:04.038933	638	320
13	2020-12-15T01:53:05.037506	179.5	360
14	2020-12-15T01:56:06.038008	359	360
15	2020-12-15T02:02:07.039348	538.5	360
16	2020-12-15T02:11:08.035850	838	420

Table 7: Resulting database of the Interference test for the HRIC channel.

EGSE_TC#	1 st acq (UTC)	Duration (s)	# acq
1	2020-12-14T23:41:00.039425	1636	819
2	2020-12-15T00:18:04.035365	1679	1680
3	2020-12-15T01:11:01.039660	1678	840
4	2020-12-15T01:48:05.036516	1679	1680

Table 8: Resulting database of the Interference test for the STC channel.

3.1.3 HKs interpretation

3.1.3.1 STC channel

Figure 2 and Figure 3 report the sensors temperature and TEC current evolution for the STC channel during the test.

Figure 2: STC Temperatures evolution over the Interference Test.

Figure 3: STC TEC current evolution over the Interference Test.

Figure 3 indicates, as expected, no peak in the TEC current once its activation and the anomalous trend due to wrong execution of the SIMBIO-SYS Thermal Settings Adjustment procedure (see [RD.4] for details).

Figure 4 and Figure 5 report the sensors temperature and TEC current evolution for the HRIC channel during the test.

3.1.3.2 HRIC channel

Figure 4: HRIC Temperatures evolution over the Interference Test.

Figure 5: HRIC TEC current evolution over the Interference Test.

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As per the STC channel, Figure 5 indicates, as expected, no peak in the TEC current once its activation and the anomalous trend due to wrong execution of the SIMBIO-SYS Thermal Settings Adjustment procedure (see [RD.4] for details).

Finally, no data are available for the VIHI channel since it was off during all the test as anticipated above and described in [RD.6].

Apart from the VIHI issue, for both HRIC and STC channels **the execution of the test has been nominal with no errors and all commanded data received correctly.**

3.1.4 Data analysis

3.1.4.1 STC channel

The 4 TCs commended in Table 8 generated four set of acquisitions with a RT of 2, 1, 2 and 1 seconds.

All the acquisitions were limited to the only Win-X.

Mean value of the window (compressed with an IBR=8) are shown in Figure 6 which reports even the RT commanded for STC and HRC (VIHI is not considered because not active).

Figure 6: In the upper plot mean DC value or for each acquisition. Bottom plot shows for the same timeline the RT commanded for STC (in RED) and for HRC (in blue)

Figure 6 clearly shows, for all STC acquisitions, the LFB effect described in [RD.11] and [RD.12].

Dividing the timeline in regions in which both cameras have a constant RT it is possible to evaluate via FFT the period of the carry wave shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Red line show the period of the low behaviour carry wave of STC for the regions with constant RT. Patches underline the error band of the measurements.

An additive noise is presents in the two cases in which HRC bring its RT from 1s to 1.5.

A zoom of one of this case is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: As for Figure 6, in the upper plot mean DC value or for each acquisition. Bottom plot shows for the same timeline the RT commanded for STC (in RED) and for HRC (in blue).

The noise is carried on a frequency of 20 Hz_{min} as shown by FFT module plotted in Figure 9.

Figure 9: FFT plots of the regions of acquisitions. High frequency peaks at 20 Hz corresponds to case: i) STC RT=1 HRIC RT=1.5 and ii) STC RT=2 HRIC RT=1.5. An higher frequency noise is lighted for HRIC RT=2.

3.1.4.2 HRIC channel

The 16 TCs commanded in Table 7 generated two sets of four acquisitions with RT = 0.5, 1, 1.5 and 2 s whose evolutions are showed in Figure 10 (first set is reported since the profile was equal as shown Figure 11).

Figure 10: HRIC 64x128 pixels average for all RT during first scale of the Interference Test.

Figure 11 *HRIC 64x128 pixels average for all RT during the four consecutive scales of the Interference Test.*

Figure 10 confirms the effect of LFB already known in previous ICOs (see [RD.11] and [RD.12]) and confirms that the **LFB effect does not depend on the RT** (event if some doubts remain due to the overlapped presence of SIMBIO-SYS Thermal Setting issue effects).

Figure 12 reports the complete data set of HRIC and compares it to the STC one: and it is evident:

1. LFB effect on STC channel does not depend on RT and its variation is due to the SIMBIO-SYS wrong Thermal Settings;
2. apparent LFB dependence on HRIC channel is due to the wrong SIMBIO-SYS Thermal Settings (see [RD.5] and [RD.4] for details).

Figure 12: Cameras LFB period variation (down) comparison with respect to WT evolution (up) (time between consecutive acquisitions which correspond to the RT for acquisitions of the same TC) during the Interference Test.

4 Conclusions

An Interference Test has been planned in ICO#04 to evaluate if parallel operations between SIMBIO-SYS channels produce some interference. In addition, the test had the secondary objective to evaluate if the LFB effect described in [RD.11] and [RD.12] was present also for the VIHI channel. Because of the issue occurred during the VIHI performance test (see [RD.6] for details), the SIMBIO-SYS Interference Test was done just with the HRIC and STC channel.

The test execution was nominal, with no errors and evidenced the following elements:

1. On both cameras, **no dependance in the oscillation period of the LFB effect with respect to RT**
2. HRIC and STC LFBs (more intense phenomena in the case of HRIC) seems increase independently by the RT during the test
3. HRIC acquisitions with $RT = 1.5s$ produce an interference on STC acquisitions that can be modelled as an additive noise with high frequency fluctuation

In any case, **due to the SIMBIO-SYS non nominal thermal conditions during the test execution and the issue occurred at VIHI, it is suggested to repeat the test in the next ICO.**